

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Innovative Sensors – Final Release

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE DN.14

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Innovative sensors and approaches for mountain catchment water balance

Introduction

The NODES project (Nord-Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile), Spoke 4 – Digital Innovation Toward Sustainable Mountain Development – tackles the key challenge of guiding water resource management into the digital era. It does so by leveraging of innovative sensors for a better understanding hydrological processes, as also illustrated by Gisolo et al. (2024). The main aim of these installations is to estimate key water balance components, such as Precipitation (P), snow water equivalent (SWE), actual evapotranspiration (AET), Discharge (Q) and volumetric water content (VWC), for study sites located in mountainous regions of Aosta Valley and Piedmont in northwestern Italy. The data collected on the experimental sites are shared as deliverable of the NODES project.

To validate the measurements obtained from innovative sensors, these were compared with data acquired through more traditional methods.

Precipitation is traditionally acquired through rain gauges, but innovative optical sensors can be deployed at monitoring sites and have the potential to reconstruct the type of precipitation together with the precipitation rate also allowing the quantification of snow water equivalent.

SWE and VWC can also be locally measured using manual measurements or through point-based capacitive sensors installed in the soil, respectively. Furthermore, to gain a deeper understanding of snowmelt processes, it is useful to employ advanced instruments capable of estimating the optical properties of the terrain (including when it is snow-covered) and vegetation.

An innovative approach for streamflow measurement involves the use of salt dilution with an automatic injection system, enabling continuous and minimally invasive discharge monitoring. Compared to traditional methods—such as velocity-area techniques to construct fixed-stage-discharge relationships — this system overcomes limitations related to manual labor, temporal resolution, and accuracy during high-flow or dynamic conditions.

To leverage advanced digital technologies, including reanalyses and satellite products, we compared measurements derived from innovative sensors with open sources gridded products (e.g., IT-SNOW, MODIS, SMAP-L4).

Moreover, measurements of electrical resistivity provide valuable insights into key subsurface properties such as water content, porosity, and salinity. To capture their spatial and temporal dynamics in a non-invasive manner, an increasingly adopted technique is Time-Lapse Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT-TL), also referred to as 4D monitoring. This geophysical method allows for the continuous observation of apparent resistivity changes in the subsurface over time (Binley and Kemna, 2005). Another technique is known as Time Domain Electromagnetic tomography (TDEM), which allows to reach deep soil layers (down to 30-40 m).

The main purpose of this report is to present the study sites where innovative sensors were installed and to illustrate the results related to the use of measurements derived from these sensors. As previously mentioned, these results include comparisons with data from traditional sensors, hydrological models, gridded, satellite-derived products, and data analysis.

The main objective of this report is to understand the reliability of the innovative sensors. Table 1 shows the results.

Table 1 Outcomes of the tests on innovative sensors.

Variable	Sensor name, manufacturer, model (if applicable)	Outcomes
Precipitation (either solid or liquid, the sensors distinguish the type)	Disdrometer, Campbell Scientific, CS125	Sensor reliable for liquid precipitation and small snowfalls. Low reliability with intense snowfalls or with dust
	Weather multi sensor, Lufft (OTT HydroMet), WS600-UMB	Sensor reliable but tends to slightly overestimate precipitation.
Snow water equivalent	Cosmic ray neutron sensor, Finapp S.p.A. CRNS	For SWE, especially at high elevation, need to be careful with calibration. Good results after new calibration for areal sensor, less reliability for local sensor: local measurements tend to underestimate SWE, but the bias can be successfully addressed with a tailored parameterization.

Snow water equivalent (cont.)	GNSS sensor, ANavS GmbH	The sensor is designed for flat surfaces. However, especially with improved calibration in 2024-2025 season, the snow water equivalent appears coherent with other sensors. The sensor tends to record unrealistic SWE values in presence of very strong winds or other phenomena that happen to change the relative position of the coupled GNSS antennas
	GPR (Ground Penetrating Radar)	Good results
Optical properties of surfaces	JB Hyperspectral Devides UG, RoX	Reliable sensor. Care has to be considered for some research on snow optical properties (e.g. select only blue sky days or white sky). Other variables (NDVI, PAR) appear reliable. On complex topographies the sensor has to be installed with care. Several effects (reflectance > 1) due to snow surface deposition changes.
	Len S.r.l. CReM	The sensor has a high power consumption and has some design flaws. The data have to be handled with care and appear noisier than RoX. Several effects (reflectance > 1) due to snow surface deposition changes.
Actual evapotranspiration	LI-COR, LI-710	The sensor yields plausible values, but tends to underestimate the turbulent fluxes
Stream discharge	Fathom Scientific, Autosalt	The sensors work correctly. For Bussoleno station the data show a noisy behaviour due to not-so-stable water level and section. At Olen Creek, results are more stable.

	<p>Flow velocity sensor, OTT Helice</p> <p>Flow velocity and discharge electromagnetic sensor, OTT MF pro</p>	<p>The measurements from these portable sensors helped to find the calibration for AutoSalt systems and also for the calibration of Arduino-based water level, temperature and electrical conductivity innovative sensors</p>
<p>Water level, temperature, electrical conductivity</p>	<p>Assembled sensors with Arduino platform</p>	<p>Reliable measurements, but software problems. Modifications of the software will be implemented.</p>
<p>Soil moisture</p>	<p>Cosmic ray neutron sensor, Finapp S.p.A. CRNS</p> <p>Point probes, Meter 10HS or EC5 (depending on the site)</p>	<p>Reliable results. Penetrating depth depends on soil moisture itself. Outliers possible. Since the sensor average a wide area, offsets compared to point probes exist, but the values are plausible and the dynamics is usually captured.</p> <p>Reliable results. Some outliers if the soil is very dry or the soil temperature is below 0°C</p>
<p>Electrical resistivity</p>	<p>Time lapse ERT with IRIS Instrument Syscal R1 and ABEM TDEM WalkTem2</p>	<p>Potential to represent deep soil moisture conditions and soil structures</p>

Lake bathymetry	GPR technology	Good results in Alpine lake depth representation
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Study sites

Nivolet (2555 m a.s.l.)

The 'Colle del Nivolet' catchment (DOR – from the river name, "Dora", Valsavarenche, Aosta Valley, Italy) is a non-glacial Alpine catchment having an area of about 17 km² with altitudes ranging from 2390 to 3400 m (Figure 1a). The catchment is characterised by Alpine grasslands. The experimental site in the catchment, at 2555 m a.s.l. is equipped with a 5-m-high eddy covariance tower equipped, at 4.6 m, with one 3D sonic anemometer (CSAT3B, Campbell Scientific) and one gas analyzer (LI-7500A, 2017-2024 and LI-7500RS from 2024, Li-Cor). On the same mast, a thermohygrometer (HMP45, Vaisala), one four component radiometer (NR01, Hukseflux) and one photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) sensor (LI190R, Li-Cor) are installed. A snow depth sensor (SR50AT, Campbell Sci.) and one terrain surface temperature sensor (S1111, Apogee) are also mounted. Two cosmic ray neutron sensors (CRNS, Finapp, S.r.l.) are also installed at the site, one on the mast (since August 2022 to measure either "areal" snow water equivalent or, in Summer, soil water content), the other on the ground to measure "local" snow water equivalent, since December 2023. At 5 m height, one present weather sensor (CS125, Campbell Sci.) was installed in late Spring 2022. Surface optical properties are detected by two instruments at roughly 3 m height: RoX (JB Hyperspectral) and CrEM (Len) since December 2023 and March 2024, respectively. The snow water equivalent (SWE) is measured with a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS, ANavS GmbH) sensor since December 2023. The Nivolet station will be soon included in the European Fluxes Database Cluster network and in Fluxnet international network. The station is already providing data for ISMN (International Soil Moisture Network). The station is also equipped with soil moisture probes at 10, 20, and 40 cm depth (10HS, Meter), two cosmic ray neutron sensors (CRNS), and TDR probes between 0- 1 m depth.

Bussoleno (650 m a.s.l.)

The 'Bussoleno-Grangia dell'Alpe' catchment (Susa Valley, Piedmont, Italy) is located between 600 and 2000 m a.s.l. with an area of 3 km² and characterized by a young, predominantly deciduous forest mainly consisting, at the experimental site within the catchment, of *Tilia* and *Castanea sativa*. The experimental site, at 650 m a.s.l. in a peri-urban forest, is equipped since March 2021 with a 25-m-high mast with an eddy covariance system mounted at 22.5 m height with one 3D sonic anemometer (CSAT3B, Campbell Scientific), one gas analyzer (LI-7500RS, Li-Cor), one four components radiometer (NR01, Vaisala) and one thermohygrometer (HMP155,

Vaisala). A vertical soil profile is investigated through soil water content probes from 10 to 200 cm depth (EC5, Meter). Two cosmic ray neutron sensors (CRNS), installed in November 2020, are mounted at 1.8 m height to monitor soil water content (within the 0-40 cm horizon) over an area of thousands of m². Under canopy, a second level of measurements is set up since February 2020, with one additional radiometer (NR01, Vaisala) and one thermohygrometer (HMP155, Vaisala). Nearby the site, on the main river of the catchment, in September 2024 a system to continuously monitor the water discharge was installed. The system is called AutoSalt (AQAc™). The station is already included in the European Fluxes Database Cluster Network and will be soon included in Fluxnet international network. The station is already providing data for ISMN (International Soil Moisture Network).

Cogne (1379-1730 m a.s.l.)

On 21 March 2025 a new station was installed nearby Cogne-Valnontey station (1682 m a.s.l.) of Centro Funzionale Valle d'Aosta. The purpose was to test the innovative sensor Lufft WS600-UMB which is an "all in one" instrument with several integrated sensors: one heated radar sensor measuring precipitation rate and type, one 2D sonic anemometer measuring wind speed and direction, one thermohygrometer measuring air temperature and relative humidity, and one air pressure sensor.

In June 2025, a new station was installed nearby the village of Epinel (Cogne, Aosta Valley, 1379 m a.s.l.). The purpose is to monitor a managed pasture all-year round. The station is equipped with the usual micrometeorological sensors as at Nivolet. However, instead of the classical eddy covariance system, an innovative sensor for measuring AET: the LI-710 (Licor).

A third station is located near the village of Gimillan (1730 m a.s.l.). The station includes one thermohygrometer (HMP45, Vaisala), one net radiometer, one surface temperature sensor (SI111, Apogee) and two soil heat flux plates (HFP01, Vaisala).

Acceglio (1650 m a.s.l.)

On 26th July 2025, an innovative sensor built by Dr. Brendan Heery and based on arduino architecture, was placed in the Maurin river, nearby Campo Base Hut, Acceglio Municipality (Maira Valley, Cuneo Province, Italy). This sensor measures water level, water temperature and electrical conductivity. Measurements campaigns were performed in Summer 2025 with OTT Helice Flow velocity sensor and OTT MF pro electromagnetic sensor for flow velocity and discharge.

Olen catchment (2050 m a.s.l.)

The Olen catchment outlet point (Alagna Valsesia, 2050 m a.s.l.) is equipped with AutoSalt automatic sensor for discharge measurements. This location has been selected due to the main interest of Monterosa 2000 (ski area) in the ecological minimum flow and in combination with measurements of other research groups.

The catchment is monitored with two experimental sites, Mosso and Passo dei Salati, as illustrated below.

Mosso (2901 m a.s.l.)

The Mosso station (2901 m a.s.l.) is located near the Mosso Institute (part of the Italian Long Term Ecosystem Research Network LTER-IT) and close to the Col D'Olen weather station managed by the Meteomont Service of the Italian Army Alpine Troops. The Mosso station has been established in October 2023. Mosso station consists of a mast with innovative sensors for measuring two variables: (i) snow water equivalent, and (ii) snow optical properties. Snow water equivalent is measured continuously since December 2023 both with GNSS (ANavS) and CRNS (Finapp) sensors. To measure snow optical properties in the visible (VIS) and Infrared (IR) bands of the electromagnetic spectrum, two sensors are deployed at Mosso: (i) RoX (JB-Hyperspectral) since October 2023, and (ii) CReM since November 2024.

Passo dei Salati (3030 m a.s.l.)

The Passo dei Salati station (3030 m a.s.l.) is an automated weather station located near the lifting facilities that connect Passo dei Salati with the Indren Glacier. The station is part of the Laboratory of Alpine Climatology (LabClima) network and became operational in October 2023. It is equipped to measure the main meteorological variables such as air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction, precipitation with weighing and tipping bucket rain gauge, and snow depth. Since December 2023 the station has been equipped with a RoX (JB-Hyperspectral) sensor to measure snow optical properties in the VIS band. Since December 2024 Passo dei Salati deploys a CReM sensor to study snow optical properties in the IR band. Between December 2023 and August 2024 snow water equivalent was monitored with a GNSS sensor (ANavS) that, afterward, has been relocated to the Garstelet station. The RoX experienced several malfunctioning episodes, while the CReM had damaged optics.

Garstelet (3455 m a.s.l.)

The Garstelet station (3455 m a.s.l.) became operational in September 2024. The station is part of the LabClima network and is located near the Mantova Hut. Garstelet records the same main weather parameters as Passo dei Salati, with the addition of air pressure, incoming, reflected, and net solar radiation both Long-Wave and Short-Wave (LW and SW). A present weather optical sensor allows measurements of type, size, and fall speed of precipitation particles. It also gives information on the visibility at the site, estimating the Meteorological Observable Range (MOR). Snow meter measurements are supported by temperature acquired by a thermometric array consisting of five thermometers installed at 50 cm vertical distance from one another. The operating range of this array goes from the ground level up to 200 cm. The Garstelet station is equipped with: (i) GNSS (ANavS) operating since September 2024 but currently not operational

due to thunderstorms in June 2025, and (ii) CRNS (Finapp) installed and operational since August 2025.

Fourcare Lake Dam (2321 m a.s.l.)

The Fourcare test site is nearby the Fourcare Lake (2321 m a.s.l., Val d'Ayas, a small valley in Valle d'Aosta Region). The Fourcare Lake is an artificial lake. This lake is used for hydropower production and for snowmaking systems.

Rutor site (2600-3400 m a.s.l.)

The Rutor glacial and peri-glacial site consists of a lake and a glacier. The lake was formed in the last 50 years, following the retreat of the front of the part of the Rutor glacier facing the La Thuile valley, at an altitude of approximately 2600 m a.s.l. The glacier is located between 2700 and 3440 m a.s.l. and it is one of the largest glaciers still existing in the Western Alps.

B) Innovative sensors for precipitation, snow water equivalent, optical properties of terrain, actual evapotranspiration, volumetric water content and electrical resistivity

Precipitation

Nivolet site

The present weather sensor (Figure 1a) reconstructs the precipitation type and the rate using a laser beam between two transducers and creating a control volume. From the different beam scattering due to particles' size and time of interference, the instrument is able to detect the falling velocity of the particle and, in combination to the particle size and air and RH temperature measurement, it also determines the precipitation type (rain, snow, drizzle). The used measurements start from 30 June 2023, when also the relative humidity values are collected.

Figure 1a) Present weather sensor mounted on the mast of the Nivolet station at roughly 5 meters high b) Installation, at Valnontey Paradisia (Cogne village) of the sensor Lufft WS600 measuring wind speed with a 2D sonic anemometer, air temperature, relative humidity, air pressure, precipitation rate and type

Results indicate a possible strong overestimation (Figure 2) of the precipitation rate in particular during heavy snowfalls and despite several data have been filtered according to either uncertain classification of precipitation types that could be related to incoherent measurements. A further filter includes periods when precipitation types are recognised by the sensor but related to mixed precipitation and snow grains, if that type of precipitation occurs within 6 hours around unidentified type of precipitation. This overestimation is confirmed also with the newly installed heated gauge at Nivolet (Campbell Sci. CS700H) in October 2025.

The CS700H appears to underestimate some precipitation event (i.e. 23 October 2025). Further investigations may be carried out to better understand this behaviour once more data are obtained throughout the snow season. The examined present weather sensor is aligned to literature findings. For instance, Lanza and Stagi (2009) found an overestimation of precipitation from optical disdrometers compared to a rain gauge. However, it should be noted that rain gauges can lead to systematic precipitation underestimation, in particular when windy conditions occur, since a part of precipitation is carried away, blown by the wind in a horizontal direction (Figure 3). Days with high average wind speed greater than can be characterised by strong underestimation of precipitation (i.e 29 October 2025). On average, above 1.5 m/s, the low wind speed condition threshold usually found in literature (Anfossi et al., 2005), the difference between disdrometer and rain gauge is 6.9 mm. Below 1.5 m/s, the difference collapses at 2.3 mm). The snow depth can offer an information about snowfalls (thus leading to precipitation data exclusion if the datum does not correspond to snow depth increase), but often the snow depth sensor does not measure correctly during the events. Problems could arise in particular events with intense snowfalls that do not deposit a significant snow layer because of too high air and soil temperatures. As suggested by Pickering et al. (2021), since a low agreement between optical instruments is found in the ability to determine drop size and velocity distributions, meteorological stations should use multiple sensors for redundancy. This suggestion may be limited due to power consumption constraints in remote areas. Further analyses might include be devoted to understand the relationship between the precipitation classification (SYNOP code), the precipitation rate detected by the CS 125 and the precipitation detected by the CS700H rain gauge.

Figure 2 Time series at the daily scale of precipitation as measured by disdrometer CS125 at Nivolet, 2555 m a.s.l.) and Rain Gauge at a station managed by Centro Funzionale (CF), Valle d'Aosta Region (Pont Valsavarenche, 1981 m a.s.l.). The Centro Funzionale station is located at a distance of about 3 km from the Nivolet station.

Figure 3 Upper panel: cumulative precipitation between October and November 2025 as measured at Nivolet (2555 m a.s.l.) by disdrometer CS125 and the rain gauge (Campbell Sci. CS700H) and as measured by Pont Valsavarenche station managed by Centro Funzionale of Aosta Valley Region. Pont station is located at 1981 m a.s.l., at a distance of about 3 km from the Nivolet station Lower panel: average daily wind speed nearby the rain gauge CS 700H

Cogne Paradisia (Valnontey) site

The Lufft WS600 was tested against the precipitation data from Valnontey, Lillaz, Grand Crot and Gimillan stations managed by Centro Funzionale of Aosta Valley. Results highlight a possible slight overestimation of precipitation by Lufft WS 600 sensor if compared to heated rain gauges, especially the one at Valnontey, very close to the innovative sensor (in that case, the overestimation is of about 40 mm by 1st December 2025 (Figure 4). This confirms that the radar technology, similarly to laser technology at the basis of the disdrometers, tends to overestimate precipitation if compared to classical bucket rain gauges. However, while optical instrument such as disdrometers may interpret dust as precipitation and may interpret wrongly heavy snowfalls, radar instruments are less affected by these problems.

Figure 4 Cumulative precipitation from four stations of Centro Funzionale Valle d'Aosta inside the Cogne Municipality and the Luftt WS600 from May to 1st December 2025.

Snow water equivalent

For this part, SWE was continuously measured at three high-elevation sites: Nivolet (Figure 5a, Figure 5b) Mosso (Figure 5c), Garstelet (Figure 5d). Two types of sensors were used, the Cosmic Rays Neutron Sensors (CRNS, Finapp S.r.l) and the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS, ANavS GmbH). Both systems reconstruct the SWE within an area around the sensor itself. The CRNS uses an established relationship between the detection of neutrons flowing from space (cosmic rays) and interacting with water molecules to reconstruct the water content in snow also by means of additional modelling. The GNSS sensor relies on the differential signal between one ground (below snow) and one mast antenna. From the differences in signal strength, the SWE can be reconstructed (Capelli et al., 2022).

Figure 5 a) Indication of RoX, CReM and ANavS systems at the Nivolet site b) CRNS installation for areal and local SWE estimates c) RoX, CReM and CRNS installation at the Mosso site d) RoX Installation at the Garstelet site. RoX. RoX and CReM instruments will be described better in Section "Terrain (snow and vegetation) optical properties".

Nivolet site

At the Nivolet station (Figure 6), in snow season 2023-2024 a low SWE was measured by GNSS system if compared to CRNS-derived SWE. A higher agreement was found between the two SWE reconstructed by the CRNS sensors, although the uncertainty of the areal sensor was high if compared to the other uncertainties, especially in the 2024 Spring. The low estimate of SWE from GNSS system might be due to some mast bending or rotation due to the snowy conditions of that season. The decreasing curves of late May 2024 are due to snowmelt. The local SWE was higher than the areal one probably because of the onset of patchy conditions detected by the CRNS giving the areal SWE. Several power interruptions occurred in Spring 2024, whereas in the following snow season (2024-2025) much less data losses occurred, as can be noticed in Figure 7. During the 2024-2025 snow season, a good agreement was observed between GNSS-derived SWE and areal SWE estimates from CRNS, while lower values were recorded by the “local” CRNS sensor. A consistent relationship was also found between SWE and snow depth measurements for the same season. In contrast, for the 2023-2024 snow season, SWE estimates from CRNS showed the highest consistency, whereas GNSS-derived SWE was less reliable due to installation issues affecting sensor performance.

Figure 6 SWE data at Nivolet station (2555 m a.s.l.) in the 2023-2024 period. Top panels: comparison of GNSS (blue), CRNS local (green), and CRNS areal (red) SWE measurements during the snow season 2023-2024. Bottom panel: snow depth measured at the site with SR50AT sensor (Campbell Sci.).

Figure 7 SWE data at Nivolet station (2555 m a.s.l.) in the 2024-2025 period. Top panels: comparison of GNSS (blue), CRNS local (green), and CRNS areal (red) SWE measurements during the snow season 2023-2024. Bottom panel: snow depth measured at the site with SR50AT sensor (Campbell Sci.).

Moreover, the DIST, DST and DISAFA groups are currently leading a study involving the network of CRNS in the Italian Alps to perform SWE measurements by the Regional Environmental Protection Agencies of Piedmont and Veneto, and the Hydrographical Office of the Bozen Autonomous Province. The focus of the study involves the parameterisations adopted to define the regression curve which translates the neutron flux into SWE. Differently from what was inferred during the 2024/2025 snow season, the Western and Eastern Alps do not actually need two different parameterisations. This finding paves the way for enhanced networking capabilities along the Alpine arc. The results have been submitted to an international peer-reviewed journal.

Mosso site

The GNSS sensor installed at the Mosso site experienced problems in 2023-2024 snow season and no data are available. In 2024-2025 snow season the sensor data exhibited minor gaps (Figure 9) between December 2024 and January 2025 due to less power shortages. These power shortages were caused by prolonged periods of low incoming solar radiation and relative energy production through solar panels that resulted in a net drainage of the batteries installed to sustain the station. This problem was addressed and resolved during the season by installing additional solar panels and batteries. The major gap of the GNSS series in the period 28/05/2025 – 16/06/2025 was due to a malfunction of the ground antenna of the sensor, which, due to unknown circumstances, was unable to retrieve satellite signals. The snow season 2024/2025 was the first to be entirely monitored at a daily timescale at the sites, filling the existing gap in the time resolution of SWE direct measurements obtained through snow coring during research field campaigns. In this

regard, during the snow season 2024/2025, the SWE measurements of the innovative sensors have been compared to the manually obtained SWE data (Figure 9).

The CRNS series monitored at the Mosso site shows several gaps in 2023-2024 snow season (Figure 8), whereas in 2024-2025 snow season it shows no major gaps until 21/06/2025 when it abruptly interrupts (Figure 9). This interruption was caused by maintenance work on the communication infrastructure present in the area, which resulted in the disruption of the signal coverage that allows the sensor to transmit data to the cloud. The problem has been resolved and, since 09/09/2025, the sensor has begun to acquire and upload new data.

Both the sensors appear to be negatively biased compared to the on-site measurements as can be seen from Figure 9. The continuously acquired data allowed the identification of accumulation and melting periods of the seasonal snow cover. The accumulation period lasted for roughly seven months from the second half of October 2024 until the first week of June 2025. Due to prolonged high temperatures the snow cover at the site completely melted in less than two months (e.g. by the second half of July).

Figure 8 SWE data at Mosso station (2901 m a.s.l.) in the period 01/09/2023 – 31/08/2024. CRNS (green), and direct (red) SWE measurements during the snow season.

Figure 9 SWE data at Mosso station (2901 m a.s.l.) in the period 01/09/2024 – 31/08/2025. GNSS (blue), CRNS (green), and direct (red) SWE measurements during the snow season.

Garstelet site

The Garstelet station (3460 m a.s.l.), installed in August 2024, experienced a severe thunderstorm on 13/06/2025. At least one lightning struck the site causing several damages. The solar panels powering the station were fatally compromised. Moreover, the rain gauge and the GNSS SWE sensor were damaged. This event resulted in a forced stop of all the station's activities that could only be addressed partially by the substitution of the power supply apparatus. Therefore, since 29/06/2025 the station started again to collect weather data, except for SWE and precipitation due to damage to the two involved sensors. A rather good agreement was found between SWE from GNSS sensor and snow depth (Figure 10).

Figure 10 SWE measured by GNSS sensor and snow depth measured by SnowVue10 (Campbell Sci.) at Garstelet station

In the month of September 2025 two CRNS sensors have been installed. The first one has been installed at the Garstelet station, where its deployment is meant to replicate the SWE monitoring setup currently employed by the Mosso station with parallel continuous SWE measurements performed by CRNS and GNSS (once the latter is repaired and operational again). The second CRNS has been installed at the Intermedia station (2654 m a.s.l.), as part of a synergistic collaboration with the PNRR Project ITINERIS-Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System. It will also be capable of measuring soil moisture data in absence of snow cover.

Figure 11 SWE measured by CRNS sensor (top panel) and snow depth (bottom panel) measured by SR50AH(Campbell Sci.) at Garstelet station

Analysis to assess a possible quality control: the example of Mosso site

For the GNSS sensor, 56 of the 286 (i.e. ~20%) available SWE data retrieved in the period 01/09/2024 – 31/08/2025 were deemed invalid after a quality control process involving the comparison with the SWE data recorded at the site by an automated weather station operated by the Meteomont Service of the Italian Army's Alpine Troops (Figure 12, top panel). The origin of these invalid data is attributable to changes in the relative position between the airborne and the ground antennas caused most probably by strong wind events. The invalid data immediately after and before the prolonged gap in the data make an exception, since they have been interpreted as being directly linked to the ground antenna malfunctioning.

For the CRNS, all the invalid data were recorded between the 1st and 6th June 2025. Figure 12 (bottom panel) and Figure 13 shows the results with the quality control. A strong geomagnetic storm was found to cause a temporary reduction in cosmic-ray flux, leading the CRNS to erroneously register a SWE spike—highlighting a key but easily manageable vulnerability of the technology.

Figure 12 SWE data at Mosso station (2901 m a.s.l.) in the period 01/09/2024 – 31/08/2025. Top panel: GNSS (blue) and direct (red) SWE measurements along with the periods of invalid GNSS data (shaded red). Bottom panel: CRNS (green) and direct (red) SWE measurements along with the period of invalid CRNS data (shaded red).

Figure 13 CRNS SWE data (blue), invalid period (shaded red), and Kp Index (colored bars) in the period 09/05/2025 - 21/06/2025. The Kp Index is color coded according reflecting the absence of geomagnetic storms ($K_p < 5$; green), the presence of minor or moderate geomagnetic storms ($5 \leq K_p < 7$; yellow), or the presence of strong geomagnetic storms ($K_p \geq 7$; red).

Snow water equivalent at the Rutor glacier

The SWE at the Rutor glacier was measured with georadar technology. The georadar survey was carried out in the months of May-June 2024, in collaboration with ARPA Val d'Aosta, aiming at estimating the Snow Water Equivalent (SWE) on a part of the Northern slope of the Rutor glacier. The data acquisition of ground penetrating radar measurements was performed with a 900 MHz antenna along a series of profiles, as shown in Figure 14a, for a total length of approximately 4500 m. The ground penetrating radar measurements were calibrated at different points using probe measurements for the accurate estimate of the seasonal snow thickness. The calibration allowed us to estimate an average velocity value of propagation of the radar waves in the snow (about 0.22 m/ns), in order to convert the radargrams into depth sections. An example of a ground penetrating radar section (radargram) is shown in Figure 14b.

Figure 14 a) disposal of the GPR transect over the glacier surface to detect the SWE on the Northern slope of the Rutor glacier; b) example of radargram to estimate the SWE at the Rutor glacier; the red line detect the boundary between the seasonal snow and the firn-ice.

The georadar profiles were collected starting from the summit area of the glacier (about 3300 m a.s.l.) up to the level of the Northern front of the glacier itself. The thickness of the seasonal snow varied between approximately 3 m and a maximum of approximately 6-7 m.

The average density values were approximately 350-400 kg/m³.

The statistical analysis of the data and the integration of the information acquired from the georadar data with the measurements from the probes are carried out by ARPA VdA; the overall interpretation is reported in the ARPA technical reports, aimed to define the mass balances of the glacier (not included in this report).

Terrain (snow and vegetation) Optical Properties

The terrain optical properties are important for studies about snow metamorphism, snow microphysics, changes of the snow surface and melting processes due to meteorological and climate factors or either sand or dust deposition (Salvatori et al., 2022). Furthermore, from the optical properties, during the growing season indexes related to the vegetation activity can be inferred, such as the NDVI. In addition, the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), the shortwave radiation used by vegetation for photosynthesis, can also be extrapolated.

The two sensors involved are: i) The JB RoX, which is a hyperspectral device operating in the optical range of the electromagnetic spectrum; ii) The CReM, which is a narrow-band spectral device operating on two bands of the infrared spectrum, namely in the Near Infrared (NIR) centred on 1250 nm wavelengths and in the Short-Wave Infrared (SWIR) centred on 1640 nm wavelengths. Both instruments are meant to investigate snowpack features such as crystals metamorphism, presence of dissolved organic carbon (DOC), presence of Saharan dust, and melting processes.

Mosso, Nivolet and Passo dei Salati sites

The JB RoX and the CReM innovative sensors were installed for the analysis of surface optical properties at three study sites: Mosso (2901 m a.s.l.), Nivolet (2555 m a.s.l.) and Passo dei Salati (3030 m a.s.l.). To obtain a self-coherent dataset to perform the analysis, among all the hourly data recorded by both instruments, the focus was on the measurements performed between 10:45 and 11:45 (UTC+1) for Mosso and Passo dei Salati sites. This choice descended from the need to intercept the highest possible irradiance values (e.g. at noon) while avoiding shading effects linked to the presence of buildings and other objects in the proximity of the sensors. Furthermore, the analysis was constrained to blue-sky days, identified by means of comparing the standard deviation of the measured irradiance at the sites with the theoretical one. For the Nivolet station, the data from 11:00 to 15:00 (UTC+1) were used. This choice was made as a trade off between the interception of high irradiance values and the need of an acceptable amount of data.

As shown in Figure 15, the RoX evidences the presence of vegetation at the Nivolet site, while it is missing at the Mosso site due to emerging bedrock and a higher persistence of the snow cover due to the higher altitude of the Mosso site than the Nivolet site. At Mosso site, the disappearance of snow on the ground is well observed through the rapid drop in reflectance across all bands. It is also a good sign that the reflectance values in each band are very similar, in agreement with the theoretical curves for snow and rock (Figure 15). The CReM also identifies the snow cover well at Mosso and Nivolet sites (Figure 16), yielding results consistent with theoretical expectations: in this case, the snow reflectivity at 1640 nm is visibly lower than at 1250 nm; the two values converge only when the underlying rock emerges, marking the end of the snow cover.

Both, the RoX and CReM at Passo dei Salati data have prolonged gaps due to malfunctioning (e.g., problems for the CReM optical elements). In this regard, a limited amount of data are shown from these sensors at this site.

Figure 15 Reflectances in different bands at the Mosso and Nivolet stations as measured by RoX.

Figure 16 Reflectances in different bands at the Mosso and Nivolet stations as measured by CReM.

Further analyses at the sites with RoX and CReM sensors

To depict the metamorphism involving settling snow crystals, reflectance in six bands were used (i.e. 405 nm, 605 nm, 805 nm, 945 nm, 1250 nm, and 1640 nm). The lowering of the reflectance in time after the last snow precipitation event at the Mosso site gives insights into the microphysical processes involving the snowpack. For this reason, for each snow event the linear trend of the reflectances against the days since the last precipitation was computed. The trends obtained for each event and band are summarised in Figure 17.

Figure 17 Linear trends of the reflectance (grey lines) at each band and their weighted averages (dashed).

To further investigate the evolution of the snowpack optical response to weather conditions, the reflectance at the selected bands was correlated with some weather parameters measured at the sites (e.g. air maximum temperature, snow height, wind speed). From the analysis, significant negative correlations with the maximum temperatures on all bands were found (Figure 18 Correlation of the reflectance at each band and the daily maximum temperature measured at Passo dei Salati (Period 01/11/2024 – 30/06/2025)). This phenomenon is probably linked with the insurgence of melting processes and will be the subject of further investigations. Moreover, snow samples are being collected to be analysed for DOC and nitrogen content. Saharan dust is also being collected and will be analysed in the next months (organic and inorganic chemistry). Future research perspectives will be aimed at defining the optical signatures of organic and inorganic compounds in the snowpack as well as determining their concentration from non-invasive measurements.

Figure 18 Correlation of the reflectance at each band and the daily maximum temperature measured at Passo dei Salati (Period 01/11/2024 – 30/06/2025).

Two time-lapse cameras have also been installed at the Mosso and Garstelet stations, to analyse the fractional snow cover. The Mosso camera was operational until May, when it was torn apart from the wall it was fixed on by a blizzard. Subsequent tries to reinstall it evidenced critical breaks in the framework so that it needs to be fully replaced. The Garstelet camera is operational and provides daily and sub-daily information on the distribution of snow cover in the investigations site (Figure 19). An automatic procedure for image elaboration is being developed.

Figure 19 Raw images acquired from the time-lapse cameras installed at Mosso (left) and Garstelet (right) stations, on 6th April 2025.

Nivolet station

For the Nivolet station, data of the hours around midday were used (i.e. between 11:00 and 15:00 UTC+1), when the maximum solar radiation is available also in Winter. Using RoX data, a decreasing trend of reflectance against surface temperature was found in six different bands, that included also wavelengths towards the extremes measured by the RoX (R between -0.16 and -0.57). The most significant trends were found for the reflectance between 405 and 805 nm, whereas the extremes showed very low R^2 and, for the 1005 nm, also a non-significant trend (Figure 20). It should be noted that the bands below 400 nm and above 980-1000 nm might be not well measured by the instrument, but were included in this analysis as an experiment. The decreasing trend is also found for CReM reflectance (Figure 21): both trends are significant, although a less negative trend, with lower significance, is found at 1640 nm if compared to the 1250 nm band. The reflectance reduction might be associated with surface melting processes of the snow.

Figure 20 Reflectance versus surface temperature in several bands (daily values between 11 and 15 UTC+1), Winter season 2024-2025.

Figure 21 Reflectance from CReM versus surface temperature (daily values between 11 and 15 UTC+1). Winter season 2024-2025.

The RoX device also yields, after the post-processing, information about photosynthetically active radiation (PAR). A good agreement with the LI190R sensor from Licor is found (Figure 22). The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) is instead shown in Figure 23, using 11-15 UTC+1 hours then aggregated at the daily scale, showing the potential of RoX also for vegetation stress analyses together with phenocams and satellite products.

Figure 22 PAR (photosynthetically active radiation) comparison between RoX and LI190R (daily values between 11 and 15 UTC+1), growing seasons 2024 and 2025 (i.e. June-September).

Figure 23 NDVI from RoX (daily values between 11 and 15 UTC+1).

Actual evapotranspiration

Nivolet, Bussoleno and Cogne-Epinel sites

The actual evapotranspiration (AET) is an important component of the hydrological balance. Several methods allow to experimentally measure it. As illustrated in Gisolo et al. (2022), mainly, the eddy covariance technique is used. It relies on the assumption that most of the heat transport occurs within turbulent structures known as eddies. Its costs and the requirement of very robust and difficult data post-processing and quality control have a deep impact, since the air turbulence needs to be studied. Scintillometers offer an alternative to eddy covariance, but again, their use is not trivial, and they still rely on optical paths to measure atmospheric turbulence due to heat exchange between the soil and the atmosphere. Scintillometers have to be coupled with other sensors (radiometers, anemometers). Scintillometers are delicate instruments and are not easily used especially in remote areas, particularly if characterised by complex terrain. The AET can be also determined as a difference of the other water balance components. However, the water storage and percolation in the soil have to be determined with high precision using lysimeters, which are invasive and employed with difficulty in experimental sites in mountainous regions. The AET measured with eddy covariance technique is available at the sites of Bussoleno ,Nivolet and Cogne-Epinel (Figure 24a,b,c, respectively). In Figure 25 and Figure 26, the measured AET is compared with the output of CLM5, a land surface model with good results.

Figure 24 a) and b) Classical eddy covariance systems deployed at the Bussoleno (23 m high mast) and Nivolet sites; c) Licor LI-710 system at Cogne-Epinel, which uses eddy covariance theory

Figure 25 Actual evapotranspiration at Nivolet site, 2019-2025 CLM is the Community Land Model, a well-known land-surface model

Figure 26 Actual evapotranspiration at Bussoleno site, 2021-2025. CLM is the Community Land Model, a well-known land-surface model

A newly developed sensor for AET measurement is the LI-710 (LiCor, USA). The manufacturer already installs in the sensor, a software which relies on eddy covariance technique, but reconstructs already the AET performing an internal post-processing, starting from the latent heat flux and the sensible heat flux. Thus, the produced dataset is ready-to-use after a quick quality control. The sensor also provides other variables, such as VPD. The sensor correctly worked during 2025 growing season.

The AET measured by the sensor is reported in Figure 27 together with H, LE and VPD. All the variables are measured by the same sensor, thus replacing multiple sensors and showing interesting possibilities.

Other variables related to AET are surface temperature, soil heat flux, net radiation, air temperature. These variables, together with VPD, wind speed and other micrometeorological variables are important as AET drivers and are also important for land surface models. Figure 28 and Figure 29 show, for Cogne-Gimillan site, several micrometeorological variables during a Summer period.

Figure 27 Cogne-Epinel variables measured in Summer 2025 by Licor Li-710 sensor a) AET, b) latent heat flux (LE); c) sensible heat flux (H); d) vapour pressure deficit (VPD).

Figure 28. Surface and air temperatures during Summer 2025 for Cogne-Gimillan station.

Figure 29 Soil temperature compared with the energy fluxes from Sun and within the soil during Summer 2025.

Stream discharge, water level, temperature and electrical conductivity measurements

AutoSalt (AQAc™), an automated salt-injection system designed by Fathom Scientific Ltd to improve streamflow measurements in challenging environments, was installed within the NODES project at two representative Alpine catchments: Rio delle Boine (Bussoleno, TO) (Figure 30) and Olen Creek (Alagna Valsesia, VC) (Figure 33). Its deployment enhances the temporal resolution and reliability of discharge observations in steep, data-scarce basins, providing a low-maintenance and scalable alternative to traditional gauging methods.

The AutoSalt system comprises a 300-litre brine tank mounted on a custom aluminum stand, a control module, a creek pressure transducer for water level sensing, two high-resolution self-logging EC-T probes (T-HRECS), and a proprietary salt injection mechanism. The AutoSalt system has been deployed at numerous locations worldwide including Canada, New Zealand, Germany, UK, France, Italy, Japan, Sweden.

The system continuously monitors creek stage and initiates salt injection based on logical rules, typically targeting the falling limb of the hydrograph to capture a broader range of flow conditions. Alternatively, it can be configured for regular injection intervals or remote activation via telemetry. Electrical conductivity (EC) data are transmitted in real-time via LoRa radios and logged locally at downstream EC-T stations. Brine volume is measured using three independent methods, ensuring accurate dose estimation.

The AutoSalt sensors were calibrated by means of two sensors that measure the river flow velocity and the discharge: the OTT Helice Velocity sensor and the OTT MF pro electromagnetic water flow meter.

Rio delle Boine catchment

Figure 30 Panels a) and b) show two high-resolution, self-logging EC-T probes (T-HRECS) installed downstream of a 300-litre brine tank mounted on a custom aluminum stand equipped with a proprietary salt injection mechanism (Panel c). The instrumentation was installed on September 6th, 2024, with the support of a representative from Fathom Scientific Ltd and Hortus S.r.l.

A total of 264 SDIQ (Salt Dilution Instantaneous Q) measurements (red crosses, Figure 31) have been collected at this site, ranging from 0.003 m³/s to 1.87 m³/s, covering the full range of observed stage. However, the hydraulic control is highly unstable, resulting in the need for eight estimated rating curves during 2024–2025, including a transition rating curve between FSL-RC20253 and FSL-RC20254 (Figure 32). Due to the instability of hydraulic control, *Fathom Scientific Ltd.* recommend establishing an additional hydrometric station in a location with more stable hydraulic conditions. Data is missing from September to December 2024.

Following a recent exchange with *Fathom Scientific Ltd.*, they considered the possibility of filling their missing data using the measurements managed by UniTO in the same catchment, via an STS/DL.OCS sensor installed a few meters upstream of the AutoSalt system. Using the filled series as the stage input to generate a rating curve (RC) hydrograph, the results are promising, and also two independent discharge measurements carried out by the Labflux team at UniTO on 16th May 2024 and 1st Aug, 2024 are consistent with the estimated flow. However, as shown in (Figure 32), the hydraulic control changes frequently, making highly uncertain the use of a single RC for flow calculations. However, this analysis is ongoing and will be updated.

Figure 31 SDIQ (Salt Dilution Instantaneous Q) measurements compared with rating curve hydrograph estimation. EC measurements are also indicated.

Figure 32 Stage-Discharge rating curves in Rio delle Boine catchment

Olen Creek catchment

Figure 33 A 300-litre brine tank mounted on a custom aluminum stand equipped with a proprietary salt injection mechanism (Panel b). Panel c) shows a high-resolution, self-logging EC-T probes (T-HRECS) installed downstream of the salt injection system. The instrumentation was installed on September 8th, 2023, with the support of a representative from Fathom Scientific Ltd (Panel b) and Prof. Stefano Ferraris of University of Torino, head of the Labflux team (Panel a).

A total of 415 SDIQ measurements (red crosses, Figure 34) have been collected, ranging from 0.02 m³/s to 3.6 m³/s, effectively covering the full range of observed stage. Three rating curves have been developed to represent the stage-discharge relationship over the period starting in August (Figure 35).

The hydrograph for Olen Creek begins in September 2023, though it includes some periods with missing data. *Fathom Scientific Ltd.* is currently working to estimate discharge during these gaps using the continuous EC (electrical conductivity) record. This approach is consistent with the methodology applied for the June to September 2025 period, which was based on a linear regression between rating curve discharge (RC Q) and EC.T data collected in May 2025. This analysis is ongoing and will be updated. SDIQ measurements from the AutoSalt system were recorded frequently—on a near-daily basis—throughout 2024. The injection interval was reduced in 2025.

Figure 34 SDIQ (Salt Dilution Instantaneous Q) measurements compared with rating curve hydrograph estimation. From June to September 2025 period discharge has been estimated based on a linear regression between rating curve discharge (RC Q) and EC.T data collected in May 2025. EC measurements are also indicated.

Figure 35 Stage-Discharge rating curves in Olen Creek catchment

Acceglio site

The innovative sensor tested in Laboratory at the beginning of July 2025 (Figure 36a) and installed on 26th July 2025 on river Maurin, nearby Campo Base Hut (Figure 36b) yielded good results in terms of water level (and water discharge), electrical conductivity and water temperature. However, it experienced software problems since 18th September 2025. Dr. Brendan Heery and the Labflux Team are working to solve the problem and to improve both the installation and the acquisition techniques. The sensor was further calibrated in the field (Figure 36c) with OTT Helice

flow velocity sensor (c) and with the OTT MF pro electromagnetic sensor for flow velocity and discharge.

Figure 36 Innovative sensor on Arduino architecture for water level, temperature and electrical conductivity: a) testing the sensor in Laboratory; b) the installation site in Winter; c) details of the installation and calibration campaign.

Soil Moisture

Nivolet and Bussoleno sites

The cosmic ray neutron sensors can be also used for the measurement of an areal soil water content referring to a shallow soil layer between down to a maximum of about 80 cm depth, depending on the soil water content (SWC) within a footprint of hundreds of metres (Brogi et al., 2025). Figure 37 shows the CRNS at Bussoleno forest.

Figure 37 a) CRNS installation for soil moisture monitoring at the Bussoleno site b) point probes installation nearby the CRNS installation at the Bussoleno site c) CRNS and soil point probes installation at the Nivolet site

The two stations involved are the Nivolet and Bussoleno stations. The latter station is characterised by a mixed mainly deciduous forest on a North-facing gentle slope in Susa Valley, Piedmont Region, at an altitude of 650 m. The CRNS sensors have been deployed at Nivolet and Bussoleno monitoring stations with the aim of reconstructing the soil water content within at least the 0-40 cm soil horizon. Figure 38 shows the soil water content at Nivolet as measured by CRNS sensor and three-point probes at 10, 20 and 40 cm depth. A rather good agreement is

found, in particular between CRNS SWC and the two shallow capacitive probes at Nivolet. A good agreement is also found between measurements and SMAP data. At Bussoleno (Figure 39) the CRNS is still in good agreement with point probes data. However, SMAP tends to overestimate the soil water content. This effect is likely due to the dense vegetation, since the microwave brightness temperature at the basis of SMAP measurements is strongly affected by vegetation and this is a known issue in literature (Park et al., 2024).

Figure 38 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm, by CRNS sensor and by SMAP satellite product for Nivolet site.

Figure 39 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm, by CRNS sensor and by SMAP satellite product for Bussoleno site.

Building a network for soil moisture in Valle d'Aosta together with Centro Funzionale, ARPA and CVA

This network aims at reconstructing the soil water content across multiple sites. The sites of Chevrère and Cogne-Epinel, installed in 2020 and 2025 respectively, together with the ARPA sites of Cogne Valnontey, Courmayeur Mont de la Saxe, Gressoney La Trinité – Eselbode, Ayas – Alpe Aventure, Ollomont-By, Pontboset-Fournier, Torgnon, and Pont Valsavarenche are used. All sites with a land cover characterised by grassland show a good agreement between SMAP satellite data and point probes. A strong mismatch in magnitude is found for Chevrère site and Torgnon

(forest), in agreement with Bussoleno site. One further station, Courmayeur Mont de la Saxe, shows a dynamics close to forest sites, although it can be classified as a mixed terrain (forest and grassland). This behavior is likely due to the forest proximity to the measurement site. All grassland sites show a good agreement between point probes and SMAP product, thus reinforcing the findings in literature (Park et al., 2024). The systematic underestimation of SWC from SMAP found at Ollomont-By shows interesting similarities to the wider results reported by Fan et al. (2020), which report a reduced SMAP-derived SWC in vegetation-disturbed areas. See Figure 40- Figure 48 for the results.

Figure 40 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm, and by SMAP satellite product for Ayas station.

Figure 41 a) Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm, by CRNS and by SMAP satellite product at “Chevrere 3100 Monte”; b) Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm, by CRNS and by SMAP satellite product at “Chevrere 3100 Valle”; c) Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm and by SMAP satellite product at “Chevrere 4000”;

Figure 42 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm and by SMAP satellite product at Cogne-Valnontey station.

Figure 43 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm and by SMAP satellite product at Courmayeur-Mont de la Saxe station.

Figure 44 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm and by SMAP satellite product at Cogne-Epinel site.

Figure 45 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm and by SMAP satellite product at Gressoney La Trinité – Eselbode station.

Figure 46 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm and by SMAP satellite product at La Thuile-Villaret station.

Figure 47 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm and by SMAP satellite product at Ollomont-By station.

Figure 48 Soil water content as measured by point probes at 10, 20, 40 cm and by SMAP satellite product at Pontboset-Fournier

Electrical resistivity

Fourcare Lake Dam

In the Fourcare Lake test site, monitoring sensors were deployed along two transects on the West and North-West sides of the earthen dam body: Line 1 with 48 electrodes, 2 m spacing; line 224 electrodes, 2 m spacing. The objective was to identify potential anomalies in the seepage process along the dam, with an investigation depth limited to approximately 10–15 m relative to the sensor installation elevation. Since the geometry is fixed, each subsequent acquisition repeats the exact same measurement sequence, allowing for a direct comparison of apparent resistivity data over time. The initial measurement, or reference model, was acquired under known, stable hydrological conditions following a period of no rainfall (October 2023). Subsequent measurements were repeated periodically (daily frequency), strictly following the identical sequence of current injection and potential reading.

Working principle and data Acquisition Methodology

In hydrogeological and pedological contexts, ERT-TL is highly effective for estimating temporal changes in soil water content, thereby monitoring dynamic processes such as infiltration, water flow, and the potential transport of contaminants (LaBrecque and Casale, 2008). The proposed methodology involves installing a permanent network of electrodes for the repeated acquisition of subsurface electrical resistivity measurements over time. These sensors are connected to a central control unit for managing measurement sequences and data storage, with remote control capabilities via a GSM link.

Time-lapse acquisition requires a measurement setup that guarantees that the electrical resistivity variations are attributable solely to changes in subsurface characteristics, and not to measurement errors or sensor displacement. This crucial requirement is met by the permanent,

fixed installation of the electrodes for the entire duration of the monitoring campaign, ensuring high measurement repeatability and accuracy.

Electrode Arrays

The electrode configuration selected for the measurement sequence must maximize measurement stability and quality, along with the investigation's resolution capacity. Specifically, experiments utilized:

- the dipole-dipole array, which provides high resolution for lateral resistivity variations.
- The Wenner-Schlumberger array, which is more sensitive to vertical resistivity changes.

The sensors used for ERT-TL are the same as standard ERT, but the main difference lies in their permanent or semi-permanent installation strategy, optimized for long-term stability.

Electrodes, typically made of stainless steel, were semi-permanently embedded to ensure a stable, low-resistance electrical connection over time. The electrodes were driven into the ground to a sufficient depth to prevent displacement due to superficial variations (e.g., thermal expansion, minor soil movements, human or animal activity). To maintain a low and stable contact resistance, fine-grained material was placed around the electrode, which was then covered and compacted to maximize the electrode-to-ground contact surface.

Acquisition System

Sensors were connected via multi-core cables to the data acquisition system. The cables were buried and mechanically protected with corrugated piping to prevent damage and degradation from atmospheric agents.

A multi-channel georesistivity meter, the Syscal Pro, was installed for permanent monitoring. This device manages the automatic switching of electrodes to perform various measurement sequences and stores the data. The system is autonomous, powered by solar panels and batteries, and includes a GSM telecontrol system for remote configuration and real-time data visualization.

Tomographic Inversion

The inversion procedure transforms the apparent resistivity matrix into a 2D model of true resistivity for the prepared profiles. Two main approaches are distinguished (Hayley et al. 2007):

1. Independent Inversion: each time-data set is inverted independently, without considering previous measurements. Disadvantage: Can introduce temporal artifacts or discontinuities not related to genuine saturation changes.
 - Time-Constrained Inversion: it stabilizes the inversion by leveraging the temporal proximity of the data. It minimizes an objective function that includes the data misfit error and a temporal regularization term that constrains the current model to be reasonably similar to the previous model.

Water Saturation Changes

Quantitative evaluation of temporal water content variations based on electrical resistivity observations relies on Archie's Law, which governs the relationship between resistivity and water content in saturated media. For unsaturated media (soils), Archie's Law is typically resolved for saturation. In the time-lapse approach, assuming invariance of porosity and minimal variations in water resistivity (ρ_w), temporal resistivity changes can be related to saturation changes.

Interpretation of Temporal Resistivity Variations

The results are presented as tomographic sections showing the temporal evolution of electrical resistivity (Figure 49). The behaviour of electrical resistivity along the dam profile is influenced by the presence of a more electrically resistive bedrock substrate, identified only in the deeper part of the section. Seasonal temperature variations can cause fluctuations in resistivity. A change of 1 °C can result in approximately a 2% variation in resistivity values. The potential phase change of liquid water into ice in the superficial layers of the embankment caused a significant increase in electrical resistivity throughout the winter monitoring period.

Figure 49 Example of resistivity cross-sections for the period between October 2023 and March 2024, Fourcare Lake Dam, Val d'Ayas; processing of data acquired using the Wenner-Schlumberger electrode array configuration.

Future Steps for Accurate Conversion

Due to the complexity of factors influencing resistivity variations, an accurate conversion of resistivity information into water content changes require:

- Correlating the resistivity sections with piezometric level data within the dam.
- Correlating results with weather data (temperature and precipitation) to verify the effect of precipitation on the resistivity behaviour of the superficial layers.
- In-depth analysis of the effects of temperature and the water phase change on resistivity distribution.

Bussoleno site

The group of DIATI department (POLITO) in March 2024 performed two campaigns in the Bussoleno site (Figure 50) for evaluating the groundwater reservoir. It is a crucial information for understanding the catchment water dynamics.

Figure 50 Plan view of the test site with disposal of the TDEM soundings and with the transect of electrical tomography (ERT) (red line, with coordinate 0 m located at Ovest).

The measurements were carried out with a Syscal R1 device – IRIS Instrument (France) – 72 channels for electrical tomography investigations and with a TDEM WalkTem2 device for the electromagnetic survey in the time domain, with a transmitting loop of 40 m x 40 m.

The electrical resistivity tomography was carried out with 72 electrodes, 3 m spacing among electrodes, with a Wenner-Schlumberger configuration array (1287 quadrupoles), and a dipole-dipole forward (1290 quadrupoles) and dipole-dipole reverse (1100 quadrupoles), with a current cycle of 250 ms.

The data processing consisted in the reconstruction of the apparent resistivity pseudosection and the inversion with ResIPy code in a Python environment.

The data collected and a metafile are also enclosed. A preliminary graph is here included in Figure 51. The values 500 – 600 ohm (dark blue) are a signal of water presence. The yellow colour is giving instead unsaturated formations, probably with old landslide boulders.

Figure 51. Electrical resistance tomography at the Bussoleno site.

The maximum investigation depth of the resistivity sections is a function of the electrode configuration, the overall length of the electrode array and the resistivity distribution of the subsoil; in this specific case, a resistivity section was obtained up to approximately 35-40 m from ground level.

The following main structures are highlighted (Figure 52):

- the top layer is characterized by electrical resistivity values in the range of (200-400 ohm m), with the presence of conductive structures in the initial and central part of the section; this response is compatible with the presence of medium-sized materials, in an abundant fine matrix; low anomalies resistivity (blue areas in the interpretative section) can be associated with possible preferential pathway of infiltration and surface recharge from of the aquifer;
- at depths between a few meters and approximately 20-25 m, high resistivity structures are highlighted, associated with the presence of coarse-sized materials, with few amount of fine matrix;
- at greater depths, the resistivity values of 500 – 600 ohm m can be associated with the presence of an aquifer (to be verified with any information regarding the electrical conductivity of the groundwater).

Figure 52 Vertical section of electrical resistivity (values in ohm m) from the inversion of the Wenner-Schlumberger data; (no topography correction) – Section West to East.

TDEM survey

The electromagnetic survey was carried out with WalkTme2 TDEM device (ABEM Instrument) were using a transmitting loop of 40 m x 40 m, a receiving coil of 10 m x 10 m, with dual moment and high moment mode acquisition for each sounding, a time window of 10 ms, and 40 samples distributed over the time window.

The data processing involved an initial stacking of the measurements, the analysis of the response curve with respect to time and the subsequent conversion into the resistivity domain; finally, we performed with the inversion with the Occam model (1D), to elaborate the vertical profile of the electrical resistivity with respect to the depth.

The interpretation of the sounding n.1 is herein reported; the low quality of the data of soundings n.2 and n.3 does not allow the quantitative processing.

In Figure 53, the observed response curve (left) and the 1D electrical resistivity model of the S1 survey are shown (plot on the right).

Figure 53 Sounding S1; left) curve of the low moment response (red) and high moment (green); right) 1D-model of electrical resistivity.

The superficial layers are characterized by high electrical resistivity values, with values above 100 ohm m; these values can be associated with the presence of coarse material with reduced presence of water.

A first electrically more conductive horizon (with resistivity in the range 30-60 ohm m, potentially hosting the groundwater, is identified at a depth between 20 m and 30 m. A second conductive formation (values around 10 ohm m) is detected at the depth between 50 m and 80 m. The resistivity values can be associated with fine (clayey) formations, but the presence of aquifer horizons cannot be excluded.

Lake Bathymetry

The bathymetry of Lake Superiore del Rutor (belonging to the Rutor site) was explored with the ground penetrating radar (GPR) technology. The survey was performed with a radio-controlled vessel, towing a GPR antenna operating at the main frequency of 200 MHz and the radar central unit. The main goal was to characterize the bathymetry of the lake and to study the bottom sediments. The lake was formed in the last 50 years, following the retreat of the front of the part of the Rutor glacier facing the La Thuile valley, at an altitude of approximately 2600 m a.s.l.

The main scientific interest is to estimate the volume of water of the basin and to estimate the sediments and sedimentation process within the basin, that could be related to the erosion and solid transport process due to the retreat of the glacier.

The main results (Figure 54) obtained are summarised as:

- characterization of the sediments in the delta area of the tributary to Lake Superior, caused by the solid transport resulting from the melting phase of the glacier;
- mapping of the lake's bathymetry, with digital data available with a mesh of 10 m x 10 m (CSV format).

Figure 54 a) Lake Superiore at Rutor, in foreground the radio-controlled boat; b) : thickness of the water column, lake Superiore at Rutor, as resulting from the interpretation of radargrams.

Assessing the reliability of innovative sensors of SWE and AET by comparison with gridded products

A Decadal (2015-2025) Analysis of Snow Water Equivalent and Evapotranspiration Patterns in Western Italian Alps: Emerging Signals of Climate Warming

European Alps are essential sources of water sustaining downstream ecosystems and human activities. In this regard, they are referred to 'the water towers of Europe' (Viviroli et al., 2007). However, these regions are also among the most sensitive to climate change. Indeed, the high rate of temperature increase (Brunetti et al., 2009), altered precipitation regimes, and "snow droughts", i.e., a lack of snow accumulation in winter, are significantly impacting the hydrological processes in snow-dominated areas (Barnett et al., 2005; Gobiet et al., 2014).

Monitoring and modeling hydrological processes in high-elevation environments remain particularly challenging due to complex terrain, limited accessibility, and sparse in-situ observations (Harpold et al., 2017; van Tiel et al., 2024).

In this context, Snow Water Equivalent (SWE) and Actual Evapotranspiration (AET) are two key variables for understanding the mountain water cycle. Investigating SWE and AET changes is essential to detect whether the hydrological cycle is accelerating in response to climate warming (Wang et al., 2023). Indeed, the altered snow accumulation dynamics can modify the partitioning of water to evapotranspiration versus runoff (Harpold et al., 2017). As a consequence, it is necessary to assess water availability and adapt water resources management across sectors such as hydropower production, drinking water supply, and irrigation (van Tiel et al., 2024).

Gridded datasets, such as those derived from reanalysis products (Avanzi et al., 2023) or satellite-based observations (Earth Science Data Systems, 2025), have significantly enhanced the spatial

representation of climatic and environmental variables in topographically complex regions (Ahamed et al., 2022). This is particularly valuable in mountainous areas, where the availability of ground-based observational data is often sparse or unevenly distributed due to logistical and environmental constraints (van Tiel et al., 2024).

In this study we investigate the dynamics of SWE and AET over the past ten years across catchments of varying spatial scales, by using gridded datasets. The analysis also includes a comparison between gridded data and in-situ measurements. The main aims are:

- assess whether these datasets are capable of capturing key hydrological processes at multiple spatial scales;
- identify potential shifts in snow regimes and evapotranspiration patterns over the ten-year period that may be attributable to climate warming;
- evaluate the extent to which gridded data can be reliably used for local-scale studies;

C) Material and Methods

Study area

A study area (hereafter referred to ROI, i.e., Region Of Interest) was selected. It encompasses the Valsavarenche and Cogne valleys in Aosta Valley region, and the Orco Valley in Piedmont region. Specifically, we selected 5 different study catchments. The first three catchments' boundaries were delineated at the outlet points of: Savara River closed at Valsavarenche Eaux-Rousses (AO), Grand-Eyvia River closed at Cogne-Cretaz (AO), and Orco River closed at Spineto (TO), where water level sensors are operated by the Functional Center of Aosta Valley, ARPA Aosta Valley, and ARPA Piedmont, respectively. Additionally, within the catchment closed at Valsavarenche Eaux-Rousses, two smaller sub-catchments monitored by the LabFlux research group of the University and Polytechnic of Turin were also considered. These sub-catchments were defined by selecting as outlet points two locations where water level sensors have been installed by the Labflux team. Indeed, a water level sensor has been installed in the Dora del Nivolet river, while an additional sensor was installed at a small spring, known as the Source del Nivolet, which discharges into the Dora del Nivolet. The geographical framework of the five catchments is shown in Figure 55, while their characteristics are reported in Table 2.

Figure 55 Geographical framework of the five study catchments

Table 2 Main characteristics of the five study catchments

Catchment Name (ID)	Outlet point Lat [°]	Outlet point Lon [°]	Area [km ²]	Mean elevation (range) [m a.s.l.]
Source del Nivolet (SOU)	45.5190	7.1767	0.16	2636 (2390-2790)
Dora del Nivolet (DOR)	45.5213	7.1798	16.99	2711 (2390-3430)
Savara at Eaux-Rousses (SAV-ER)	45.5668	7.2084	80.93	2701 (1650-4057)
Grand-Eyvia at Cretaz (GEY-C)	45.6145	7.3405	174.4	2589 (1473-4055)
Orco at Spineto (ORC-S)	45.3867	7.6742	666.3	1842 (355-3729)

The selected catchments cover a wide range of elevations and drainage areas, from the small headwater catchment of Source del Nivolet (0.16 km², 2390–2790 m a.s.l.) to the large Orco at Spineto basin (666.3 km², 355–3729 m a.s.l.). This variability enables the investigation of SWE and AET dynamics across multiple spatial scales and elevational gradients, where dominant hydrological processes may differ significantly due to topographic, climatic, and land cover heterogeneity.

SWE and AET gridded datasets

Obtaining gridded information on key hydrological variables such as AET and SWE at large spatial and temporal scales is essential for assessing water availability and understanding how the mountain water cycle responds to climate change. These spatially distributed datasets allow for the monitoring of hydrological processes across complex terrain, and their accuracy can be significantly improved through validation with in-situ observations.

For the region of interest (ROI; see Figure 55), we retrieved two gridded datasets covering the period from 01 September 2015 to 01 September 2025, focusing on SWE and AET as the main variables of interest. The reference dataset for SWE is IT-SNOW (Avanzi et al., 2023), a high-

resolution (500 m) snow reanalysis product that provides daily estimates of snow water equivalent (SWE) across Italy for the period 2010–2025 with future updates envisaged on an annual basis. Developed as part of an operational civil protection system, IT-SNOW combines data from thousands of automatic weather stations, satellite-based snow cover products (Sentinel-2, MODIS, H SAF), and spatialized in-situ snow measurements. The dataset has been validated against both Sentinel-1 and ground-based observations, showing good agreement, and has demonstrated strong correlations with annual streamflow across over 100 Italian catchments, making it a valuable tool for hydrological studies in a changing climate (Avanzi et al., 2023).

The reference dataset for AET is the MODIS-based ImageCollection "MODIS/061/MOD16A2GF", available on Google Earth Engine (GEE) (Gorelick et al., 2017). It provides 8-day composite estimates of actual evapotranspiration (AET) at a spatial resolution of 500 meters. Each AET value represents the cumulative evapotranspiration over the preceding 8-day period, with the time series resetting annually from January 1st. The MOD16A2GF Version 6.1 product is derived from the Terra MODIS sensor and is produced at the end of each year, once the full set of input data—including vegetation indices (LAI/FPAR from MOD15A2H), albedo, and land cover—has been validated. The algorithm used to generate AET is based on the Penman-Monteith approach, integrating MODIS remote sensing products with daily meteorological reanalysis data (Earth Science Data Systems, 2025)

AET data over the ROI were retrieved using a Google Colab notebook connected to the GEE API, while SWE data were directly downloaded from the official Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/records/7034956>) and then clipped over the ROI through a Matlab script. Both datasets were originally in the EPSG:4326 geographic coordinate system and were reprojected to UTM/WGS84 (EPSG:32632) using the nearest neighbor resampling algorithm. This operation has been performed through the *reproject2utm* command available in Matlab TopoToolbox (Schwanghart and Scherler, 2014).

SWE and AET in-situ measurements

To support the validation and evaluation of these gridded products, several in-situ measurement systems were deployed across the DOR catchment. As described above, innovative sensors such as Cosmic Ray Neutron Sensing (CRNS) and Automatic Near-surface Acquisition of Volumetric SWE (ANAVS) systems have been installed to independently estimate SWE on a small plateau (Lat: 45.5191, Lon: 7.1714) within the DOR catchment. For AET, direct measurements of latent heat fluxes are available from an eddy covariance tower installed in the same small plateau of DOR catchment in November 2017 (Gisolo et al., 2022, 2025), while a Li-710 system is installed in a grassland area (Lat: 45.6314, Lon: 7.3173) near Cogne-Epinel (AO) for measuring evapotranspiration. Although the Cogne-Epinel station is located outside the defined ROI, it lies in close proximity to the GEY-C catchment and has been operational since 28 July 2025, providing an additional ground-based reference point for validating the gridded AET dataset.

D) Results and discussion

Hydrological Patterns and Climate-Driven Shifts Across Scales

The analysis of SWE and AET dynamics at the catchment scale is presented in Figure 56. To identify potential shifts in snow regimes and evapotranspiration patterns over the ten-year period (Sep 2015 – Sep 2025, hereafter P_{1-2}) that may be attributable to climate warming, we divided the study period into two parts: the first spanning from September 2015 to August 2020 (Period 1, hereafter P_1), and the second from September 2020 to August 2025 (Period 2, hereafter P_2). Given this division, we computed monthly averages of SWE and monthly cumulative values of AET for each year within P_{1-2} . Then, we calculated the multi-year monthly average and standard deviation of both SWE and AET for both P_1 and P_2 , separately. While a ten-year time span is too short to attribute observed changes strictly to climate change, some notable differences in SWE e AET between P_1 and P_2 nonetheless emerged.

In this context, it is worth noting that, during the second period (P_2), monthly mean SWE values were consistently lower than those observed in the first period (P_1). This indicates that, on average, less snow was accumulated in the snowpack during P_2 . The decreasing snow storage observed in P_2 is consistent with expected increase of air temperature (Jenicek et al., 2016). Furthermore, while standard deviations were relatively high from March to June—reflecting enhanced interannual variability in SWE, as also found by Avanzi et al. (2023) for 7 major Italian catchments (Po, Adige, Piave, Tagliamento, Tevere, Aterno-Pescara and Sangro)—in the winter months (September to January), SWE was systematically lower in P_2 compared to P_1 , with a noticeably smaller standard deviation. This pattern suggests the occurrence of what is commonly referred to as a snow drought (Harpold et al., 2017; Hatchett et al., 2017; Huning and AghaKouchak, 2020; Wiesnet, 1981), characterized by anomalously low snow accumulation during the winter season. Snow droughts can be driven either by below-normal precipitation (dry snow droughts) or by above-normal temperatures that inhibit snow accumulation despite precipitation (warm snow droughts). Both types can result in reduced summer streamflow (Musselman et al., 2017), though their hydrological signatures differ: while warm snow droughts may lead to increased winter runoff due to rainfall or rain-on-snow events, dry snow droughts typically suppress streamflow throughout the year (Musselman et al., 2017). Although the specific type of snow drought was not investigated in this study, future research should aim to distinguish between these mechanisms, as they have different implications for water resources management. For instance, dry snow droughts are particularly concerning due to their association with low reservoir levels, reduced hydropower generation, and—in severe cases—shortages in drinking and irrigation water supply (Basilio Hazas et al., 2022). Understanding the nature of snow droughts is therefore critical for the sustainable management of ecosystem services and water availability under changing climatic conditions.

On average, there is no clear evidence of an earlier onset of the snowmelt period between P_1 and P_2 . What can be observed, however, is that between March and April, although a reduction in

SWE is visible in P_1 , the decrease appears more abrupt during P_2 . This may be attributed to a relatively recent accumulation of wet snow, which has a lower retention capacity within the snowpack. What is instead clearly apparent is a slower snowmelt during P_2 compared to $P_{1,2}$. This result is in agreement with previous outcomes by Harpold et al. (2017) and Musselman et al. (2017). This outcome is supported by linear regression lines fitted from May (considered the start of the melt period) to the end of the season, which concludes in August for SOU and DOR, and in October for SAV-ER, GEY-C, and ORC-S. In all cases, the slope of the regression line is steeper in P_1 than in P_2 . This trend is consistent across all catchments, although the differences in slope become less pronounced when moving from smaller to larger catchments (see in particular Figure 56 panels a, b, and c). Overall, these results point to a shift toward a more intermittent snowmelt pattern during P_2 , which can significantly influence soil water infiltration processes and plant water uptake dynamics.

Analysis of the AET data (Figure 56, panels f to j) reveals two main observations. First, across all catchments, a general reduction in actual evapotranspiration is observed in April during period P_2 compared to P_1 . This result can be explained by the differing snowmelt dynamics in April between the two periods. As previously noted, the melt was more rapid in April during P_2 than in P_1 . Typically, when snowmelt input is concentrated over time, the resulting water saturates the soil profile more quickly and percolates deeply (Earman et al., 2006), becoming less available to plants and the upper soil layers. Conversely, when melt input is less concentrated—such as in April of P_1 —percolation is slower, and the meltwater remains more accessible to vegetation, especially at the onset of the growing season (Nehemy et al., 2022). The second notable observation is that from May to July, AET is higher during period P_2 compared to P_1 . This finding is consistent with the "drought paradox" described by Mastrotheodoros et al. (2020), where, under a climate change scenario involving a temperature increase of +3 °C and during dry years, an increase in AET was observed across the Alps during the growing season.

Figure 56 Monthly Snow Water Equivalent (SWE, top row) and Actual Evapotranspiration (AET, bottom row) over two five-year periods (Sep 2015–Aug 2020 in blue/green and Sep 2020–Aug 2025 in gray/orange) across five Alpine catchments (SOU, DOR, SAV-ER, GEY-C, ORC-S). Shaded areas indicate ± 1 standard deviation. Dashed lines in SWE panels (a–e) represent linear trends during the melt season for each period.

Reliability of Gridded Data at the Local Scale

Finally, the gridded product data were compared with in-situ measurements from monitoring stations located at Colle del Nivolet and Cogne-Epinel. As previously mentioned, both SWE and AET products could be validated at Colle del Nivolet, where measurements for both variables are available, whereas at Cogne-Epinel, only the AET product could be validated. The comparison results for Colle del Nivolet are shown in Figure 57.

The comparison of SWE measurements obtained from innovative instruments such as CRNS and ANAVS has already been presented in the above sections. What is particularly noteworthy here are the discrepancies between the in-situ measurements and the gridded products. For this comparison, the time series of the single grid cell (500 × 500 m) containing the monitoring station coordinates was extracted and compared with the time series of CRNS and ANAVS sensors in the period from Oct 2023 to Aug 2025.

Figure 57 Comparison between gridded and in-situ measurements of (a) Snow Water Equivalent (SWE) and (b) Actual Evapotranspiration (AET) at the Colle del Nivolet monitoring site. In panel (a), SWE from the IT-SNOW gridded dataset is shown alongside CRNS (areal and local) and ANAVS measurements. In panel (b), MODIS-derived AET is compared with aggregated Eddy covariance measurements. Cumulative AET is also shown for both sources (right axis). Red dashed lines highlight key reference dates (02-Jun-2024 for SWE and 08-Apr-2024 for AET) illustrating observed discrepancies.

Overall, the SWE dynamics (Figure 57a) appear to be consistent across data sources, although the absolute SWE values can vary significantly. One of the most striking differences is a delay in the timing of snowmelt in the gridded dataset compared to the local measurements. These discrepancies may stem from various factors, including uncertainties related to both the instruments and the IT-SNOW dataset (Avanzi et al., 2023). However, it is difficult to attribute the observed differences to any single cause with certainty. What can be demonstrated, instead, is a relationship between the SWE values provided by the gridded dataset and the specific characteristics of the area covered by the extracted grid cell (Figure 58a). Figure 58a shows the IT-SNOW grid cell in which the measurement sensors are located. As can be seen, the area of the grid cell extends well beyond the footprint of the innovative sensors. Using 2 June 2024 as a reference, although the sensors indicate SWE values approaching the end of the melt period, the IT-SNOW dataset reports SWE values corresponding instead to the onset of snowmelt. This discrepancy arises because the grid cell has a mean elevation of 2561.74 m a.s.l., with elevations ranging from 2391.53 to 2756.25 m a.s.l. Therefore, while snow has already disappeared in the vicinity of the monitoring station, it remains present at higher elevations within the same pixel. As a result, the pixel-average SWE (the value provided by IT-SNOW) is higher than the localized SWE captured by the CRNS and ANAVS sensor footprints. A similar line of reasoning can be applied to explain the discrepancies between the evapotranspiration measured by the eddy covariance tower and the MODIS gridded dataset (Figure 58b). Naturally, part of the disagreement can be attributed to instrumental uncertainties and to model-related errors inherent in the MODIS-derived AET product. Beyond these factors, it is notable that the largest

discrepancies occur during the spring months. Again, by considering the MODIS pixel and using 8 April 2024 as a reference, it can be observed that snow cover had already disappeared at lower elevations, while it remained present near the monitoring station (Figure 58b). As a result, soil evaporation could begin earlier at lower elevations compared to the surroundings of the station. Indeed, from the end of June onwards, once the entire pixel is snow-free, the time series from the eddy covariance station and the MODIS product show improved agreement.

Figure 58 Location of the Eddy covariance tower and in-situ sensors (CRNS, ANAVS) within the IT-SNOW and MODIS grid cell at the Colle del Nivolet site. The red dot marks the monitoring station, and the blue square represents the 500 × 500 m grid cell from which SWE and AET values were extracted. Background imagery shows Sentinel-2 true color composites for two representative dates: (a) 02 June 2024 and (b) 08 April 2024. These dates were selected as examples of periods when notable discrepancies were observed between gridded products and in-situ measurements. The spatial heterogeneity visible within the grid cell—particularly variations in snow cover—highlights the influence of intra-pixel variability in explaining such differences. Orange lines represent elevation contours.

Finally, we compared the MODIS gridded dataset with data from the Cogne-Epinel station, where AET is directly measured using the LI-710 system. As the station has been operational only since 28 July 2025, the available data are limited. Nevertheless, a good agreement is observed between the two datasets, although MODIS appears to overestimate AET relative to the LI-710 measurements (Figure 59a). In this case, the discrepancies may be explained by the fact that the MODIS pixel encompassing the station includes a substantial portion of forested area, whereas the station itself is installed in a grassland adjacent to the forest (Figure 59b).

Figure 59 Comparison between MODIS-derived and in-situ AET at the Cogne-Epinel site over August–September 2025. Panel (a) shows 8-day aggregated AET values from the MODIS product and from the LI-710 system installed at the site. Panel (b) indicates the location of the LI-710 system (red dot) within the 500 × 500 m grid cell used for AET extraction (blue square), overlaid on a Google Satellite background. The image highlights land cover heterogeneity within the grid cell, which may explain observed differences between gridded and local measurements.

E) Conclusions

This study aimed to (1) assess whether gridded datasets can capture key hydrological processes across multiple spatial scales, (2) identify potential shifts in snow regimes and evapotranspiration patterns over a ten-year period potentially linked to climate warming, and (3) evaluate the reliability of these datasets for local-scale studies.

The results show that both datasets used—IT-SNOW for snow water equivalent (SWE) and MODIS for actual evapotranspiration—successfully meet the first two objectives. Despite the relatively short study period (September 2015–August 2025), which is generally insufficient for definitive climate change detection, clear shifts in SWE dynamics and AET patterns were observed. These shifts are consistent with trends reported in the broader scientific literature under climate warming scenarios. In particular, the two five-year sub-periods analyzed appear representative of contrasting hydroclimatic conditions: the earlier period (2015–2020) reflects relatively wetter conditions, while the more recent period (2020–2025), which includes the widespread European drought of 2022, is marked by drier conditions.

Moreover, the results highlight the importance of spatial scale in interpreting hydrological processes. Notably, differences in snowmelt dynamics became more apparent when comparing catchments of varying size, underscoring the value of multi-scale analysis. One significant outcome is the detection of snow drought signals even within the present-day data, indicating that these events are already evident in current conditions. Further research is needed to formally classify and understand the characteristics of these snow droughts.

With regard to the third objective—evaluating the suitability of gridded datasets for local-scale studies—some limitations emerge. Although the spatial resolution of IT-SNOW and MODIS is relatively high compared to commonly used products like ERA5-Land (11 km), discrepancies were noted when comparing these datasets with innovative sensor data. For instance, the area covered by a single grid cell often includes diverse land cover and elevation ranges, which do not necessarily align with the footprint of local measurement systems (e.g., CRNS, ANAVS, or the LI-

710 system). This can result in systematic differences, particularly during transitional periods such as snowmelt or early spring.

Nevertheless, the gridded datasets generally capture similar dynamics to those observed by the innovative sensors. This opens up promising opportunities for integrating gridded and in-situ data—for example, using machine learning approaches to gap-fill missing ground measurements. More broadly, gridded datasets enable spatially continuous coverage over regions lacking ground observations and thus represent a powerful tool for basin-scale hydrological modeling and water resource assessment.

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